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Cover image created using OpenAI's DALL-E for the purpose of illustrating the concept of managing and publishing synthetic research data.

Managing and publishing synthetic research data

This document provides guidance on organizing and documenting datasets that contain synthetic data to simplify publication in a research data repository. Unlike datasets collected from the "real world", synthetic data often require additional details to facilitate reproduction and reuse. This document summarizes the essential information that you should provide when sharing synthetic data in a research data repository to ensure that the data can be easily understood and efficiently reused by others.

In many cases, synthetic data must be handled differently if it is based on personal data, and a section specifically addressing synthetic personal data is included.

What is synthetic data?

Synthetic data is artificial data that is generated from original data and a model that is trained to reproduce the characteristics and structure of the original data¹. It may also be partially or entirely generated from artificial sources, such as statistical distribution models or random number generators. Thus, synthetic data does not refer to a single type of data contained in files with specific formats. Rather, synthetic data are a category of data generated through particular methods.

The [EU Publications Vocabulary](#) defines synthetic data as:

Data that is (artificially) created entirely or partially for use in tests, and to meet specific needs or conditions in the real world that (existing) real-world data may not represent, e.g., anonymized datasets, typically used for proof of concept or simulation.

Thus, some data may count as synthetic data according to some definitions but not according to other definitions.

In this document, we concentrate on synthetic data that are generated based on samples of real data using machine learning techniques like generative adversarial networks (GANs) or diffusion models, but the advice is also relevant for data generated from empirical-statistical methods, resampling algorithms, or distribution fitting. Many of the recommendations are even relevant for simulated data that are created using algorithms that do not remix or resample real data.

The term *augmented data* refers to a combination of real data and artificially generated new data. Augmented data are often used to train machine learning models. It is important to note that mixing synthetic and original data within a single dataset can create challenges when publishing in repositories, as discussed below.

Note that anonymized data are not the same as synthetic personal data. Anonymized data refers to data that have been stripped of personally identifiable information so that individuals cannot be re-identified, not even with access to additional sources of information. Anonymized data thus originates from real-world personal information but undergoes modification to protect privacy. Synthetic data, on the other hand, are created artificially. If a synthetic dataset is created using personal data but contains no personally-identifiable information then it is

¹ [Synthetic Data](#) (European Data Protection Supervisor)

neither personal data nor anonymized data, but for simplicity we refer to such data as “synthetic personal data”.

Creating synthetic data

Here are some considerations to keep in mind when creating synthetic data. If you take these into account when creating data, it will make it much easier to share your data via a research data repository later!

Structure and packaging

An important consideration is file and folder structure. Separate the real data used for model creation, real data used for model verification, and synthetic data into distinct folders. Clearly differentiate input files, output files, code, and documentation. For multi-step processes, create subfolders for each step, if necessary.

You should consider how the dataset and workflow can be structured to ensure reproducibility and effective reuse. It can help to think in terms of:

- **Replication:** Include detailed workflow descriptions, code comments, record random seeds, software versions, and package dependencies. Consider version control strategies for tracking modifications in dataset generation.
- **Packaging:** Consider using virtual environments or container images to ensure that a user may gain access to an identical programming setup. Define versions and dependencies of the software environment using a standard metadata format, such as requirements files (e.g., requirements.txt) or CodeMeta documents.
- **Documentation for reuse:** Describe the data creation process clearly, including workflows and any modifications made to existing models or methods. Use an appropriate level of detail so that others will be able to modify the workflow for their own purposes. Literate programming (using a programming environment with interleaved code, documentation and output generation, such as Jupyter Notebook or R Markdown) is a great way to explain the data generation process.

Record your progress

While you are creating and analyzing synthetic data, record your observations about the model and data characteristics. The exploratory graphs and figures that you create to help you understand the dataset (but which will not be included in your research article) can also help others to understand the characteristics of the dataset. Keep a record of aspects such as:

- the relationships within the data: what aspects of the original dataset were preserved, and which were omitted or ignored?
- does the model contain chaotic or non-linear features?
- does the dataset replicate errors from the original dataset, or has it been configured to eliminate them?
- were any specific, targeted tweaks or adjustments applied to the dataset (for example, to avoid patterns originating from a certain outlier in the input data)?

Write the documentation while you are creating the data! If you wait with documentation until you start to prepare a dataset for a repository, there is a risk that you will have forgotten details!

Contributing a dataset to a research data repository

Preparing synthetic data for a repository

Clearly describe synthetic data creation using the metadata fields that are available for the repository. Check if the repository has a metadata checkbox for synthetic or augmented data. If not, use relevant keywords.

If the synthetic data is linked to real data, avoid mixing both within the same dataset. This is particularly important if the real data are personal data, as it will probably result in all the data having restricted access. Instead, publish two related datasets: one restricted-access dataset with the real data, and one openly accessible dataset with the synthetic data.

Even if the real data used to train the model can be made openly available, there are still advantages in publishing the real and synthetic data as separate datasets. The datasets can be labelled more precisely as real or synthetic with metadata. Further, if an improved version of the synthetic data is created later, having it in a separate dataset makes versioning easier. The relations between real and synthetic datasets and the specific versions being used should also be expressed in the metadata, preferably using persistent identifiers.

Documentation requirements

The primary documentation for research datasets is often a research article, where the methods section explains how the dataset was created. However, research articles are often concise, and additional documentation may be needed to ensure the dataset is described with enough detail to enable reuse.

When contributing a dataset with synthetic data to a research data repository, you should ensure that the data quality and any limitations are well documented. Describe the quality checks that you applied to ensure that synthetic data retain useful statistical properties, such as simulations or statistical comparisons. Include relevant metrics that assess how well the synthetic data represent real-world data.

Additionally, include factors that may impact the dataset's usability, such as how edge cases are handled, potential biases, fidelity concerns, and any modifications made to the model that influence data accuracy. Explicitly outline any known biases, missing features, or constraints in the dataset.

When working with synthetic personal data, document potential risks concerning re-identification (for example through calculating k-anonymity) and any specific measures taken to protect privacy. Clearly state any trade-offs between maintaining data fidelity and ensuring privacy, helping users understand the limitations and implications for the dataset.

You may need to provide guidance on the ethical implications of reusing your synthetic data for other purposes. For example, synthetic data created to train machine learning models in one domain (e.g., healthcare) might introduce biases or unintended consequences if used in

another domain (e.g., finance). Clearly documenting these potential risks helps ensure responsible reuse and mitigates ethical concerns.

As with any dataset, you should describe the provenance and versioning of your work. Clearly attribute any sources you relied on and document any iterations or updates of the synthetic data or data-generation methodology.

Finally, remember to mention any relevant data protection regulations (e.g., GDPR) that impact how the data or data-generation workflow can be used or shared.

Special considerations for synthetic personal data

Datasets that are trained on personal data are usually described with the inherently self-contradictory term “synthetic personal data”. Creating synthetic data using personal information – or using any sensitive information – requires additional safeguards.

One of the primary considerations with synthetic personal data is the risk of identification – that the synthetic data may (in some cases) be so realistic as to allow identification of individuals in the real data that were used to train the model. To mitigate the risk of identification:

- document re-identification risk assessments with metrics such as k-anonymity and quantify differences from the original dataset.
- consider how outliers affect identification risks.
- consider your fidelity requirements. High fidelity to the original dataset can increase identification risks, and high fidelity is not always needed or even desirable.

In addition, consider:

- Folder structure: If original data are sensitive and cannot be shared, consider providing an empty placeholder file or a low-fidelity synthetic dataset.
- Providing sample data: When datasets require restricted access, a zero-risk “sample dataset” may help users understand the data before applying for full access.
- Metadata and codebooks: You can make synthetic survey data easier to reuse by describing variables in a standard-format codebook rather than in a generic text file.

README file recommendations

A README is a guide to your dataset. The purpose of a README file is to assist other researchers to understand your dataset, how its content is structured, and how to use the data.

If the repository you contribute to supports rich metadata (Title, Description, Authors, Affiliations, Funding Acknowledgements, etc.) then avoid duplicating such metadata in the README file. Instead, focus on the specific details of the data and how the files and folders are structured.

Essential README contents

A README file for any dataset should include some essential elements that enable the dataset to be identified and to let users know what they can do with it. The elements listed here are not specific to synthetic data.

- **Dataset title, creators and collaborations:** The title of the dataset should be included, along with details of its creators and any collaborations involved in its development. Along with basic attribution, this makes it possible to find the dataset's catalog entry in a research data repository.
- **A persistent identifier, often a DOI (Digital Object Identifier):** If the repository displays a reserved DOI for the dataset while you are preparing your dataset submission, you can include the DOI in the README. But remember to update the DOI if you release a new version of the dataset!
- The **subject and purpose** of the dataset should be briefly described to help users understand the dataset's context and relevance.
- Information on the **software used to generate the data** should be provided, ensuring reproducibility. Provide a link to the source code if it is available on a code repository. Refer to persistent identifiers if available.
- Describe the **licensing** or **terms of use**.
- Describe any **access restrictions**. If copies of the dataset cannot be legally redistributed by third parties (for example, because of sensitive data) indicate how copies can be legally obtained.
- Additionally, any **considerations regarding reuse**, such as potential limitations or best practices, should be mentioned.

If not provided in a separate file, a sample of the data can be included to give users an overview of the dataset's structure and contents.

Additional README information for synthetic data

For synthetic datasets, we recommend that you include some information about how the dataset was created and validated. You do not need to include lots of details in the README, especially if details are already described in other documentation files! However, it is important to let the dataset user know that you have validated the data, and where they can find more information.

- **Production details:** Describe the generative model used, and the raw data sources. Were any specific code configurations used to generate the data? List code parameters and seeds.
- **Intended realism:** Is the synthetic data meant to be realistic, or is abstraction the goal?
- **Data selection.** Briefly describe how the training and testing data were selected.

- **Validation methods:** Summarize how the synthetic data were compared to the real data (e.g., simulations, statistical comparisons) and where the results of these comparisons can be found (if not in the README).
- **Content quality considerations:** Describe any particular aspects of the dataset that may affect its usability, including how edge cases are handled, potential fidelity concerns or biases, any modifications made to the model that impact data fidelity, and considerations for k-anonymity when dealing with synthetic personal data. Where appropriate, detailed information can be provided in a separate documentation file, but the README should indicate that the information is available.
- **Sensitive data considerations:** Note any specific data intersections that may pose risks.

In summary

This document identifies the primary data generation, documentation, and ethical issues to consider when managing and publishing synthetic research data. The key best practices are really the same as for any other data: maintaining clear file organization, providing thorough metadata, and documenting both the data creation process and the actual data.

Synthetic datasets, however, can have limitations or biases that are not present in their real-world counterparts. When dealing with synthetic personal data, additional safeguards must be in place to assess and mitigate re-identification risks. But by systematically documenting data generation and validation methods, and by being transparent about known biases and data limitations, you can ensure that your synthetic data can be responsibly shared and meaningfully reused.

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Additional resources.

For more information on the complexities of synthetic data and tools for testing and labelling, see [Synthetic data for Open Science](#) (Fair Ai Data).